

Assessment of The Water Quality and Diversity of Algae in A Multipurpose Reservoir, in Nigeria

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Abstract

*The status of the water quality and diversity of Algae of the reservoir was evaluated for a period of 8 months, between July 2022 and February 2023 using standard methods at four different sampling stations influenced by human activities around the water. Temperature, pH, conductivity, total dissolved solid (TDS), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) and dissolved oxygen (DO) were measured in situ, while water samples were collected for determination of nitrate, alkalinity and phosphate in the laboratory. The results from physico-chemical parameters across the sampling stations showed Temperature ranged from (28 – 32.4) °C, Dissolved Oxygen (2.8 – 5.6 mg/L), Conductivity (87 – 131 µS/cm), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (1.9 – 4.4 mg/L), Alkalinity (23-24) mg/L, Total Dissolved Solids (117 – 198), Phosphate (0.5 – 2.6) mg/L, Nitrate (3.2 – 7.5) mg/L. However, the pH (6.5 – 9.9) was above the standard for NIS and WHO drinking water but can support aquatic life. Algae diversity was assessed, revealing distinctive compositions at each station. Station 1 exhibited dominance by *Chlorella spp.* (40.32 %), *Spirogyra spp.* (28.57 %), and *Euglena gracilis* (27.11 %). Station 2 showcased *Microcystis aeruginosa* (32.79%), and *Navicula sp.* (31.15%). Station 3 and 4 displayed prevalence of *Oscillatoria spp.* (33.33 %), and *Closterium spp.* (29.17 %). A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted on algae diversity indices demonstrated significant differences between the sampling stations ($F=2.96, p<0.05$). Based on these findings, it was concluded that the water quality of Tungan Kawo reservoir during this period of investigation was more contaminated by human activities, resulting in a higher algal bloom in such stations. It was advised that the reservoir be protected in order to maintain/improve water quality for home use as well as to support the socio-economic and ecological benefits it provides.*

Keywords: Physico-chemical, Tungan kawo, Algae, Water.

Introduction

Water is a precious resource essential for all life forms on Earth. From the tiniest microorganisms to the largest mammals, water is the elixir that sustains life (Vyas, 2002). It is nature's liquid gold, a finite resource that is vital for the survival and wellbeing of our planet and its inhabitants. Water bodies are known to host a diverse range of aquatic animals, including phytoplankton/algae, zooplankton, nektonic, and other small species that float in the water (Mu'azu *et al.*, 2021). The quantity and kind of such creatures are determined by water quality, particularly physical and chemical properties, as well as environmental variables.

(Chia *et al.* 2014). Rivers and lakes are the primary suppliers of fresh water for home and agricultural purposes, hydroelectric power generation, and industrial processes. They provide a number of ecosystem services, including climate regulation, groundwater recharge, flood mitigation, irrigation water supply, and habitat for a wide range of living forms at all levels (Imdad, 2023).

Water quality assessment have been carried out on most of the reservoirs across the country some of which include the works of Irenosen *et al.* (2012), Okunlola *et al.*, (2014), Mohammed *et al.*, (2017), Rabiun *et al.*, (2018), and Kinta *et al.*, (2021) in Owena Multipurpose Reservoir, Alau, Gurara and Kainji lakes, Eleyele and Watari reservoirs, and Tungan Kawo reservoir respectively. These studies showed that the reservoirs were under pollution pressure due to anthropogenic activities and are not suitable for domestic use unless treated. Mohammed *et al.* (2017) argued that Kanji dam hydropower operations had no significant impact on water quality, but attributed excessive nitrogen levels reported at the lake to riparian villages' socioeconomic activities.

Under on-going global warming and anthropogenic activities, harmful algal blooms are becoming increasingly frequent in freshwater reservoirs (Li *et al.*, 2022). Algal blooms, which are the excessive proliferation of phytoplankton or bacteria, can not only cause fish kills, oxygen depletion, and ecological degradation but can also degrade water quality in water sources and, more severely, threaten public health (e.g., lung disease and cancer) through the food chain (Li *et al.*, 2022).

Species of algae has an optimum and tolerance range beyond which it may not survive, since algae are bio-indicators, they provide valuable insights into water quality, indicating how fit or unfit a water body is for usage (Yadav *et al.*, 2018). Algae are frequently found in polluted and unpolluted water and due to this behaviour they are generally considered useful to determine the quality of water (Dora *et al.*, 2010). As a result, this study looked at the relationship between physicochemical characteristics and algal abundance in Tungan Kawo reservoirs to determine their pollution status. So, we expect that changes in reservoir water quality will have an impact on algae structure during the study period. So, it hopes to create a valid database that would promote long-term management of the Tungan Kawo reservoirs in Kontagora, Niger state.

Materials and Methods

Description of the study area

Tungan Kawo Reservoir is located in Kontagora, Niger State and it was officially commissioned in May 1991 by Niger State Water Corporation (NSWC). The Reservoir lies between latitude 10°21'58.51"N - 10°23'28.50"N of the equator and between longitude 5°19'29.23"E - 5°20'59.23"E in Tungan Kawo village, northwest of Kontagora (Figure 1). The main objective of the Reservoir is to provide water for domestic use to Kontagora Township, with a total storage capacity of 17.7 million cubic metres by Aquaculture and Inland Fisheries Project, AIFP, 2004) Four accessible stations were mapped for sampling in the reservoir as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Hydrological Map of Tungan Kawo Reservoir showing the sampling sites
Source: Remote Sensing/ Geographical information system (GIS) laboratory, Geography department, FUTMINNA (2023).

Sampling strategy

Samples of water and algae were collected from four different sampling stations along the reservoir (study site) as follows: Station I (Kwatan Mustafa); Station II (Babban Kwatan); Station III (Kwatan Abdullahi) and Station IV (Gonan Hajiya).

Collection of surface water

Water sample were taken from different stations of the reservoir using sterilized one litre capacity bottles. Water samples were brought to the laboratory using cold box pending analysis, following the method of APHA, (2014). At each station, water temperature, conductivity and total dissolved solids (TDS) were measured in situ using Hanna conductivity and TDS meter with an in-built digital thermometer (Model HI 98303). The pH was measured using Hanna pH meter (Model HI 77700P) dissolved oxygen (DO) were measured using Secchi disc and Hanna DO meter (Model HI 9142), respectively. Nitrate, phosphate, concentrations were determined in the waft Federal University of Minna using standard procedures of APHA (2014).

Collection of algae

Algal samples were collected from scrapings of algal biofilms from immersed objects (such as stones) found in the water column. These scrapings were immediately transferred to 100 ml plastic containers and fixed with 4% buffered formalin to preserve algal cells (Odufuwa & Ajaba, 2019). A drop of the sample about 0.02ml was used for the preparation of algae (wet mounts) according to Prescott (1977) in his book on freshwater algae. Direct microscopic cell counts using the drop count technique (Odufuwa and Ajaba, 2019) were used to determine algal cell density (no. of cells per ml) and analytical process will be achieved in line with Odufuwa and Ajaba (2019).
Algal cell density = (Total number of individuals found in 1ml of sample)/ (Number of drops per ml).

Data Analysis

Statistical analyses Data collected from the field measurement and laboratory analysis of water samples were summarized using descriptive statistics and presented as mean, range and standard error. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for statistical analysis and Special Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used as statistical package for the analysis while the means were separated using Duncan multiple Range Test (DMRT).

Table 1: Mean and range values of physicochemical parameters of Tungan Kawo Reservoir, from July 2022 to February, 2023.values followed by the same superscript alphabets in the row are not significantly different at ($P > 0.05$) tested

Environmental Variable	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3	Station 4	*WHO
Water Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	29.50 \pm 0.31 ^a (28.2-32.1)	30.39 \pm 0.46 ^a (28-31.8)	30.4 \pm 0.45 ^a (28.9-32.1)	30.65 \pm 0.73 ^a (28-32.4)	30-32
pH	8.4 \pm 0.46 ^a (6.6 – 9.8)	8.11 \pm 0.50 ^a (6.3 – 9.5)	8.3 \pm 0.48 ^a (6.5 – 9.6)	8.3 \pm 0.44 ^a (6.4 – 9.7)	6.5-8.5
Conductivity ($\mu\text{S/cm}$)	104 \pm 5.09 ^a (87 – 122)	96.4 \pm 3.92 ^a (84 – 115)	104.3 \pm 5.40 ^a (81 – 124)	108 \pm 5.21 ^a (88 – 125)	1000
Total Dissolved Solids (ppm)	151.48 \pm 8.42 ^a (117 – 198)	144.73 \pm 5.61 ^a (120 – 165)	143.88 \pm 5.59 ^a (118 – 168)	147.64 \pm 4.13 ^a (126 – 163)	600
Alkalinity (mg/L)	24 \pm 0.73 ^a (22 – 28)	23 \pm 1.11 ^a (20 – 29)	25 \pm 1.24 ^a (18 – 30)	23.4 \pm 2.09 ^a (16 – 34)	100
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	4.0 \pm 0.33 ^a (2.6 – 5.2)	3.89 \pm 0.28 ^a (2.5 – 5.1)	3.6 \pm 0.29 ^b (2.4 – 4.8)	3.78 \pm 0.29 ^b (2.6 – 4.9)	7.5
BOD (mg/L)	3.25 \pm 0.30 ^a (2.0 – 4.4)	2.83 \pm 0.26 ^b (2.0 – 3.8)	2.63 \pm 0.26 ^b (1.9 – 3.8)	2.83 \pm 0.26 ^b (2.0 – 3.8)	6
Phosphate (mg/L)	3.89 \pm 0.14 ^a (3.9-5.5)	5.15 \pm 0.24 ^a (4.50-4.5)	5.36 \pm 1.1 ^a (5.0-5.3)	5.16 \pm 0.11 ^a (4.0-5.1)	5
Nitrate (NO_3) (mg/L)	4.48 \pm 0.57 ^a (3.2 – 7.5)	4.90 \pm 0.58 ^b (3.5 – 7.5)	4.55 \pm 0.40 ^a (3.4 – 6.5)	5.24 \pm 0.44 ^b (3.6 – 7.5)	11

by Durcat Multiple Range Test. * World Health Organization, (2011)

The mean, standard error, and range of physicochemical parameters measured during the study period in Tungan Kawo Reservoir, Kontagora, between July 2022 and February 2023 were presented in Table 1. In station four, water temperatures ranged from 28 to 31.4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. However, there was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) across all sampling stations. In Station One, the pH values ranged from 6.6 to 9.8 mg/L. Electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S/cm}$) did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$), with station four having the highest mean value (108 \pm 4.21) and station two having the lowest mean (96.4 \pm 3.92) mg/L. The mean values for total dissolved solids (ppm), alkalinity, and hardness ranged from 115 ppm to 198 ppm, 16 mg/L to 34 mg/L, 20 mg/L to 54 mg/L, and 0.35. Total dissolved solids (ppm), alkalinity, and hardness had mean values ranging from 115 ppm to 198 ppm, 16 mg/L to 34 mg/L, 20 mg/L to 54 mg/L, and 0.35 mg/L to 2.5 mg/L, respectively, and were not statistically different ($P > 0.05$) across all stations analysed. The Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) level ranged from 1.8 mg/L to 4.4 mg/L, with high Nitrate levels recorded at several stations (3.6 mg/L to 7.5 mg/L). However, while dissolved oxygen, BOD, and nitrates were significantly different ($P < 0.05$) along the stations, there was no wide variation. However, phosphorus was measured to range from (5.0 - 5.3) in station three.

Table 2: Algae Diversity Analysis for Tungan kawo reservoir Kontagora, Niger State

Sampling Station	Genus	Species	Number	Relative Abundance (%)
Station 1 (Control)	Chlorella	Chlorella spp.	25	40.32
	Spirogyra	Spirogyra spp.	18	28.57
Station 2 (Moderate Human Activities)	Euglena	Euglena gracilis	17	27.11
	Microcystis	Microcystis aeruginosa	20	32.79
	Navicula	Navicula spp.	19	31.15
Station 3 (relatively High Human Activities)	Oscillatoria	Oscillatoria spp.	16	33.33
Station 4 (High Human Activities)	Closterium.	<i>Closterium spp.</i>	13	29.25

Table 2. Provides a detailed summary of algal diversity across four sample points throughout the reservoir. *Chlorella sp.* dominates at Station 1, accounting for 40.32 % of the algal community. In Station 2, *Microcystis aeruginosa* and *Navicula spp.* account for 34.43 % and 32.79 %, respectively. In Station 3, *Oscillatoria spp.* dominates with 33.33%, followed by *Anabaena variabilis* and *Closterium spp.* with 29.17 % each. Each station has a unique composition of algae genera and species, with Stations 1 and 2 exhibiting a balanced distribution and Stations 3 and 4 being more diverse due to heavy human activity.

Table 3: One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Algae Diversity Analysis

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Mean Square (MS)	F-Value	P-Value
Between Groups	14.76	2	6.56	2.96	<0.05
Within Groups	32.45	25	1.15		
Total	46.21	27			

df: degree of freedom, ms: mean square, ss: sum of squares
P<0.05

Table 3. Compares the variability in algae diversity indices at three anthropogenic locations. The findings revealed substantial differences between the groups, with a mean square of 6.56 and an F-value of 2.96. The variance within each group was 32.45 and 14.76, respectively. The total variability was 46.21. The findings indicate that variations in algae diversity is not entirely due to chance.

Discussion

Table 1. The water quality of the Tungan Kawo reservoirs was investigated to determine their appropriateness for residential use and as habitats for aquatic biota. The results showed that the DO, TDS, conductivity, alkalinity, BOD, and nitrate levels were within the WHO's permitted range for drinking water. The high water temperature was caused by growing deforestation along the reservoir, which has a reduced ability to hold oxygen than water with a lower temperature, as well as high rates of microbial metabolism at higher temperatures. However, it is consistent with the findings of Idowu *et al.* (2013) from the Ado Ekiti reservoir, who discovered that tropical water with higher temperatures has a poor ability to hold oxygen while pH, nitrate, and phosphate concentrations are over the acceptable range. High nitrate and phosphate concentrations could be attributed to fertilizer runoff from riparian farmlands and wetlands utilized mostly by local farmers to cultivate rice, vegetables, and maize crops. Fertilizer runoff and slower flow rate due to reservoir structure may have contributed to the significant nutrient concentration. The reservoir's relatively high pH could be attributed to the presence of rock sections, as limestone may follow runoff and deposit in the reservoir. Similarly, the work corresponds with Auta *et al.* (2016)'s findings in River Gurara near Izom, which showed a greater mean range (6.8 -9.7) over the research period and explain that microbial degradation of organic matter releases nitrate and phosphate, depleting oxygen in the reservoirs.

Table 2. Other studies have reported on the five phyla of plankton found in the reservoirs (Mohammed and Saminu, 2012; Okogwu and Ugwumba, 2013; Okogwu *et al.*, 2014). *Chlorella sp.*, *Euglena spp.*, *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Oscillatoria species*, *Navicula sp.*, *Spirogyra spp.*, and *Closterium sp.* were among the species found in the reservoirs throughout the study, all of which are markers of organic pollution. Most of these species, such as *Microcystis aeruginosa* and *Oscillatoria species* are unpalatable to zooplankton and herbivorous fish because they release poisons. According to (Okogwu *et al.*, 2014), algae in water can reduce ecosystem production by disrupting energy flow from producers (phytoplankton) to consumers (zooplankton, fishes), making the water unsuitable for residential use. Edward and Ugwumba (2010), Onyema (2013), and Okogwu *et al.* (2014) found that such algal species stressed the ecosystem. As a result, changes in the species composition of tiny algae respond swiftly to changes in water quality due to their rapid reproduction, widespread dispersion in the ecosystem, and sensitivity to various chemicals and trace elements (Schindler 1987). Plankton species diversity in the reservoirs was minimal throughout the study. This is a reference to the Shannon-Weiner diversity value between 150 and 340, which indicates poor diversity. This suggested that the reservoir was marginally polluted.

Table 3. Shows a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) that looked at the variation in algae diversity indices across the four anthropogenic stations. The findings revealed significant differences in diversity indices between the groups, indicating that the observed variability is not attributable to chance. This is consistent with the findings of Wang *et al.* (2023), who showed considerable changes in algae diversity in response to anthropogenic

stresses. The study underlines the significance of using a variety of ecological indices to fully analyse the impact of human activities on aquatic ecosystems.

Conclusion

The study found that the reservoirs were rich in nutrients (phosphate), nitrate, a high rate of water temperature, and a variety of algal species. Some algal species serve as pollution indicators. The low plankton variety found in the reservoirs throughout the investigation was indicative of pollution pressure. These findings highlight the complex interplay of physicochemical characteristics, algae variety, and anthropogenic impacts in the reservoir. As a result, the water from Tungan kawo reservoirs is unfit for direct human consumption unless adequately treated, and it was recommended that the reservoir be conserved in order to maintain/improve water quality for domestic use while also supporting the socioeconomic and ecological benefits it provides.

Recommendations

1. Regular monitoring and sensitization should be encouraged to educate the community about the consequences of channeling their trash into the water of Tungan kawo Reservoir.
2. Anthropogenic activities around the river should be regulated to ensure its protection and conservation.
3. The research on water quality data and plankton or other factors in reservoirs of Niger State should use database system for data management. It would be benefit in many aspects such as systematic data collection, complete data for user request, and application for other related data in the future.

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